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Comment on Saif's Survey of Pakistan Construction Industry on the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor

Bell, Peter

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Abstract

The historic strategy of global resource imperialism, implemented by the 2013 Belt and Road Initiative from the People's Republic of China, has set a new competitive landscape for economic development worldwide, and the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor is a priority case study for the impacts of rapidly modernizing local transportation networks, energy infrastructure, and the economy. It is essential to track local attitudes towards these government programs, as in the research by Saif, Meixia, and Saleem (2023) from Dalian Jiaotong University, which provides survey results from construction industry participants in Pakistan during this ongoing massive infrastructure investment program.

Keywords: Surveys, Belt and Road Initiative, CPEC (China-Pakistan Economic Corridor), Construction industry, Transnational operation management, Sustainability, Environmental impact, Economic impact, Investment, Technology transfer, Infrastructure development, Stakeholder engagement, Governance, Capacity building, Innovation

JEL Codes:

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Comment on Saif's Survey of Pakistan Construction Industry on the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor

The historic strategy of global resource imperialism, implemented by the 2013 Belt and Road Initiative from the People's Republic of China, has set a new competitive landscape for economic development worldwide, and the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor is a priority case study for the impacts of rapidly modernizing local transportation networks, energy infrastructure, and the economy. It is essential to track local attitudes towards these government programs, as in the research by Saif, Meixia, and Saleem (2023) from Dalian Jiaotong University, which provides survey results from construction industry participants in Pakistan during this ongoing massive infrastructure investment program.

The survey results suggest that industry and government unanimously support China's investment. This sets an important precedent for the global reputation of the Belt and Road Initiative. The negative attitudes noted are “exacerbated environmental and social issues related to the construction sector, including health and safety risks, displacement, pollution, and land acquisition,” highlighting important issues that impact infrastructure development worldwide. These same problems are relevant to places like Canada today because the shape of future world trade is built on infrastructure, legal frameworks, and the flow of capital today.

The survey results must note the negative impacts on environmental and social issues, as these affect the political profile of the entire program. Construction projects have direct and immediate effects on local people. For example, a new road increases activity in the area and raises incomes broadly, but locals may suffer from increased pollution. There can be tradeoffs between broadly felt benefits and local problems. The survey results are unclear on how to address these problems, but it does mention increased stakeholder engagement as a thematic topic to mitigate problems. There are winners and losers in development, and this survey focuses on winners in the construction industry who are close to the economic action. Could a survey with a broader participant base yield useful insights into the negative impacts of these infrastructure programs? It is important to understand the negative impacts of these programs because of their large scale and innovative features.

Understanding the winners and losers from infrastructure investment is a major priority in Canada today. For example, the oil industry in the Province of Alberta needs more transportation capacity to increase production, but the Province of BC has been slow to allow further pipelines. These are complicated domestic political issues between neighbouring provinces within the same country, which is different from the international relationship between Pakistan and China. Surveys are always an important tool for gaining insight into the strengths and weaknesses of government programs, and can be useful in Canada for infrastructure projects.

The Province of BC may be slow to approve new pipelines and associated infrastructure because the provincial leadership is focused on potential negative local environmental impacts of increased pipeline build-out. Or the provincial leadership may also consider that bituminous oil from Alberta has a larger environmental footprint than other sources of oil around the world, and BC may be taking a stand on a global environmental issue with these local political decisions? How do we expand the discussion of Alberta's oil to consider other sources of oil production around the world, like Russia? Does the decision of BC to *de facto* limit Alberta's total oil and gas production cause an increase in production from other countries, and how does that factor into local provincial politics within BC? The way Alberta and BC need leadership from the federal Canadian government to coordinate decision-making may be similar to the way China provides leadership in this program in Pakistan.

There is an opportunity for political leadership to create a new framework in Canada that changes how infrastructure projects are delivered over the next century. Can we put First Nations first? The Pakistan survey shows top priorities are health and safety risks, displacement, pollution, and land acquisition. Are these also the top concerns for Canadians? Consider, for example, how the Supreme Court of BC is forcing provincial governments to address fundamental legal questions of land ownership with First Nations through its August 2025 decision granting Aboriginal title to land in the City of Richmond. This raises fundamental questions about property rights and presents opportunities for significant changes to fundamental aspects of the legal basis for BC. Will these changes lead to further innovations, like special

economic zones in BC or a new policy to allow foreign direct investment? Surveys of participants in the Belt and Road Initiative provide an important perspective for Canadian policymakers seeking to understand the global competitive landscape for international business development opportunities.

There are also incremental changes happening in BC around how a prospector stakes a mining exploration claim. Originally, claims were staked by prospectors physically putting posts into the ground at the claim site. Today, claims are staked online, and the government consults with relevant First Nations before issuing the claims. I understand that consultation is legally required, and this looks like consultation, but I would point out that it's not ownership! Are these changes in BC examples of effective stakeholder engagement? The surveys from Pakistan (Saif, Meixia, Saleem, 2023) repeatedly emphasize that stakeholder engagement is an essential factor for the success of these infrastructure projects, but provide very few details on what good engagement looks like. Again, there are political opportunities for BC to set new standards by creating new methods for stakeholder engagement in the modern information age. How do we access the wisdom of the crowds to improve SWOT type analysis of proposed infrastructure projects? We may not be ready to crowd-source the decisions yet, but can we use digital communications technology to improve the quantity and quality of conversations around major development project decisions? Can we compare how "stakeholder engagement" consultation happens in Pakistan around the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor with what is happening in Canada now?

Saif, Meixia, and Saleem (2023) could expand on the thematic finding that infrastructure spending programs have led local governments in Pakistan to change their rules. Were there any instances where different levels of government had conflicting rules around infrastructure development planning and execution? There are opportunities to improve regulatory frameworks around infrastructure in Canada and BC, too. For example, the BC government could make a drastic simplification to the taxation of mining projects to include only a 10% production royalty payable to the BC government from mining, where the government used half these royalty payments as government revenue and the other half to fund a sovereign wealth fund for First

Nations in BC. This may cause a significant shortfall in tax revenues for the BC government relative to the current permitting framework, but my goal with this idea is to fundamentally shift the industry's economic basis in a way that incentivizes production at world-leading standards.

As part of this change to the taxation of mining in BC, imagine if the government also set new requirements for environmental impacts that do not define them in terms of dollars spent, but instead in terms of reducing pollution? If the province starts an extensive program of ongoing environmental baseline monitoring around current and historic mines, it could actually have objective, public information to guide policy decisions with greater transparency.

Could the Province of BC create Special Economic Zones to imitate part of the Belt and Road Initiative playbook, where foreign companies have specialized laws for operations in a specific geographic area? What if BC applied these policy ideas to an entire industry rather than a geographic area, such as creating a new policy framework to incentivize the mining business in BC? It is important to redesign government policies at all levels to align constraints with priorities, especially amid increasingly complex arrangements for new sources of funding for infrastructure development. The Belt and Road Initiative is an important example of international finance for infrastructure development, and it represents an innovative form of foreign direct investment.

Saif, Meixia, and Saleem (2023) suggest the survey results are unanimous: the construction industry in Pakistan is positive towards China and the Belt and Road Initiative. I think this result is expected because infrastructure funding can be compared to a “resource boom,” such as the discovery of new oil or metal deposits. I would like to see this survey campaign expanded and repeated to investigate whether these impressions have become more positive over time or not? Have the surveys found that concerns over safety have increased over time or not? Is it possible to collect these surveys over time and identify surveys that function like a natural experiment to understand how the infrastructure funding affects attitudes? These surveys provide useful information on the attitudes towards the Belt and Road Initiative elsewhere around the world.

To further understand the profile of the Belt and Road Initiative on a global basis, I would like to understand how the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor impacts GDP. Can we identify the direct impacts of each project using a detailed breakdown of total costs? What are the indirect impacts of the increased local incomes associated with the spending? What are the indirect impacts of the new infrastructure and increased economic activity over the life of the infrastructure? It is important to develop new methods to estimate these impacts and answer questions about the sensitivity of economic growth to infrastructure. The potential to find projects where government spending on infrastructure creates a large multiplier effect on GDP over time is a priority in Canada today, especially in the context of increasing trade with new countries and trading blocs around the world.

The surveys of local construction players do not highlight national sovereignty as a significant concern. Saif, Meixia, and Saleem (2023, p. 7) describe how this topic appears in the academic literature, particularly around government debt: “Estimates suggest that CPEC-related debt could reach \$90 billion, accounting for approximately 40% of Pakistan's GDP.” How does Pakistan's debt-to-GDP ratio compare with those of other countries that experienced significant foreign direct investment in infrastructure throughout history? How much will this infrastructure affect GDP growth, and will the government be able to collect sufficient taxes to pay the debt?

There is an estimate of the GDP impacts of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor by Ali, Huang, and Xie (2022), in an article that focuses on Pakistan’s agricultural industries. They write, *“Our results show that due to transport infrastructure development, the GDP and welfare of both Pakistan and China will improve, with a maximum of 0.3% and 0.01% increase in GDP, and USD 2.6 billion and USD 1.8 billion gains in welfare for Pakistan and China.”* I was astonished to hear that Pakistan’s benefit was measured at \$2.6 billion compared with the estimated \$90 billion increase in Pakistan’s national debt (Saif, Meixia, and Saleem (2023, p. 7)? These estimates provide a framework for assessing the sensitivity of GDP growth to infrastructure spending, but care is required to separate timing from amounts accurately.

A report from the World Bank (2020) provides a longer-term perspective on the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor, tracing it back to the China-Pakistan Free Trade Agreement,

first signed in 2007. This report does not include estimates of the programs' GDP impact. The Government of Pakistan (2020) fact book provides further qualitative insights into the impacts of infrastructure projects. Still, there is an opportunity for governments to provide greater detail about the economic effects of these programs.

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